

OPTIMIZATION OF EXTRACT PRODUCTION FROM *CURCUMA LONGA***Ismoilov Sh.F.¹****Kayumov F.S.²**

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: shohrux.farruxovich98@gmail.com

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Relevance: phytotherapy based on medicinal plants is one of the oldest therapeutic practices in human history and still holds an important place in modern medicine. Today, there is an increasing demand for natural preparations that are ecologically safe, low in toxicity, and highly biologically active. In particular, the use of medicinal plants rich in flavonoids and other bioactive compounds is widespread in the prevention and treatment of liver diseases. One such plant is *Curcuma longa* (turmeric), whose main bioactive substances — curcumin and flavonoids — possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and hepatoprotective properties. Traditional extraction methods are often time-consuming and energy-intensive, and may not ensure sufficient yields of bioactive compounds. Therefore, ultrasonic extraction technology is of particular importance due to its efficiency and energy-saving advantages.

Aim of the study: the main aim of the research is to develop a technology for obtaining dry extract rich in bioactive compounds from *Curcuma longa* using ultrasonic extraction, to determine the optimal solvent system, to evaluate the efficiency of the extraction process, and to study the physicochemical and technological properties of the resulting dry extract.

Materials and Methods: the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* were used as raw material. Various solvents purified water, 50% ethanol, and 70% ethanol were tested for extraction. Ultrasonic bath extraction was carried out for 15, 30, 45, and 60 minutes. Different raw material-to-solvent ratios (ranging from 1:2 to 1:7) were examined to identify the most effective proportion. The obtained liquid extracts were centrifuged to remove ballast substances, then dried under vacuum at 105 ± 5 °C to produce a dry extract. The product was evaluated for moisture content, particle size, flowability, bulk density, granulometric composition, and angle of repose, in order to assess its pharmaceutical applicability.

Results: according to the study results, ultrasonic extraction at 40–50 °C and a raw material-to-solvent ratio of 1:6 provided the most efficient outcome. Among the tested solvents, 50% ethanol demonstrated the highest extraction yield of bioactive compounds (up to 16.81%). Although 70% ethanol also showed high yields, 50% ethanol was considered the most energy-efficient option. The dry extract obtained was a yellow, hygroscopic powder with a characteristic odor, and its particle size ranged between 0.16–0.37 mm. In terms of granulometric composition, the $-1000+500\mu\text{m}$ fraction predominated (33.29%). Flowability was measured at $2.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg/s, the angle of repose was 55.49°, and residual moisture content was 4.2%.

Conclusions: the study demonstrated that ultrasonic extraction of *Curcuma longa* is an effective and energy-saving method for obtaining dry extract. The use of 50% ethanol as a solvent was found to be the most optimal, ensuring maximum yield of bioactive compounds. The proposed technology enables the production of high-quality dry extract, which can be practically applied in the pharmaceutical industry for the development of hepatoprotective, antioxidant, and other bioactive preparations. In the future, the obtained extract can serve as a promising basis for the creation of new dosage forms in pharmaceutical manufacturing.